

High priority use-cases

Weather and climate models are highly complex and generate vast amounts of data. With many legacy simulations, new techniques & approaches are developed for exascale

Fusion modelling: NEPTUNE aims to simulate the plasma in the outer regions of tokamak confinement devices, including its interaction with solid walls

Community contributed: 10 design and development working groups were stood up to explore and define high priority exascale use cases, such as turbulence modelling (right)

Cross cutting research

Identify and solve challenges that cut across our high priority use-cases and must be solved to reach exascale supercomputing

Each project lasts three years and works with several use-cases to help address a range of exascale software development challenges

These cross-cutting projects include

- IO & storage
- Data workflows
- Code coupling
- Domain Specific Language
- Verification, Validation and Uncertainty Quantification
- Parallelism in time
- Task-based parallelism
- Machine Learning (ML) for computational workloads
- Future computing paradigms
- Exascale computational imaging

What is ExCALIBUR?

Started: October 2019
Finishes: March 2025

A UK research programme aiming to deliver the next generation of high-performance exascale simulation software for the highest priority fields

Emerging requirements for HPC algorithms

There are a variety of communities who are not currently large scale users of HPC, but would benefit from the exascale supercomputing. ExCALIBUR has identified new communities and emerging requirements to help open up exascale more widely

These include:

- Biomolecular simulations
- Agent-based Modelling for Policy Evaluation in Real-time
- Biomedicine Engagement
- Bio-image processing

Knowledge Exchange

Exchanging knowledge throughout the programme and wider HPC community is crucial to ensuring that the work undertaken can be exploited by others. All projects have a Knowledge Exchange Coordinator (KEC) and effort set aside for knowledge exchange activities

Having people with skills to program future exascale supercomputers is crucial, and the programme has funded RSE training projects to develop and deliver training materials

Leveraging ARCHER2 throughout the programme

Individual projects have relied heavily on the UK's fleet of current generation supercomputers, especially ARCHER2

Furthermore, software developed and optimised during eCSE projects has greatly benefitted many of the ExCALIBUR projects

Hardware and Enabling Software (H&ES)

We have recently seen an explosion in novel hardware architectures. Largely driven by the desire to deliver increased performance and energy efficiency for AI/ML workloads, a key question is their role in future exascale supercomputers.

There are eighteen novel hardware testbeds

- Available to the rest of the program and wider scientific software developers
- Include quantum, RISC-V, FPGAs, CGRAs, CS-2, Rockport, Graphcore, and Next Silicon.
- Software efforts funded to support these, such as porting common HPC libraries, tooling, and standardised benchmarking

We are keen to connect and collaborate!

<https://excaliur.ac.uk>
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